

CONSCIENTIZING EXTENSION: MVGFC- CEOPs IMPACT ON THE LIVES OF THE PEOPLE IN BARANGAY TALIPAPA, CABANATUAN CITY, NUEVA ECIIJA

Rene Boy E. Abiva, MA-MP, D. Litt. (Hon. Causa), Abegail Dela Cruz,
Dr. Federico O. Perez, Dr. Soledad M. Roguel, and Dr. Ingrid F. Calanno

Institute of Teacher Education, Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

A meaningful, relevant, and sustainable community extension, and outreach program (CEOP) is an integral component of the development program of a Higher Education Institution (HEI). A community extension and outreach program along the expertise and programs of the institution is a major requirement not only for the accreditation of programs which accrediting agencies such as the Philippine Association of Colleges and Universities Commission on Accreditation (PACUCOA) look for but also the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Just like any other HEIs, Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges, Inc. (MVGFCI) would like to engage in a sustainable outreach program to help improve the lives of marginalized individuals, families, and the community. However, the search for a barangay which will accept, cooperate, and sustain the development efforts of the institution for the community has been a challenge in the past for the institution. CEOP activities for the barangays chosen were either changed or terminated and therefore not sustainable. But in 2019, the college officially adopted Barangay Talipapa in Cabanatuan City to embark its new set of programs. MVGFCs CEOP is anchored from our Research, Development and Extension (RD/E) Agenda which is focused on poverty alleviation. MVGFC believes that the marginalized sector in our society needs support for them to “stand at their own” and given the time and opportunity, improved quality life could materialize if the proper programs for them are formulated and implemented. This research highlights the effectiveness of Community-Based Participatory Action Research (CBPAR) as an efficient tool not only in the field of research but also in increasing ontological collective action. The paper also emphasizes the importance of the CEOP as a framework for understanding the relationship between education, community extension

and outreach programs, and individual and social transformation. MVGFCs CEOP demonstrate the power of critical pedagogy and community engagement in promoting transformative and emancipatory learning. By involving the community in problem-solving and co-creation of knowledge, MVGFCs CEOP was able to achieve a more inclusive and participatory approach to development. The research provides valuable insights into the importance of engaging with communities in a meaningful way and the role of education in promoting individual and social change.

Keywords: *Community Extension and Outreach Program, Community-Based Participatory Action Research (CBPAR), Talipapa, COVID-19, Academic and community alignment*

INTRODUCTION

Education has had a dual purpose throughout history, aiming to enlighten people's consciences and shape the minds of future generations, impacting interpersonal interactions, communities, and societies. However, globalization has transformed people's perspectives and the way they perceive the world, leading to changes in education's mission, function, orientation, and structure (Avoseh M., 2009).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) play a critical role in achieving the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Development Goals, particularly in the areas of universal education and community development. However, these institutions face the challenge of re-establishing critical examination as the foundation of education and breaking free from the constraints of tyranny. To achieve this, they must leverage sociocultural structures and relationships to advance their goals. The history of Community Extension Services (CES) in colleges and universities sheds light on how it has impacted student life, education, and human conscience. The Spanish missionaries established "Model Farms" or "settlement farm schools" during the 333-year colonization from 1521 to 1854, according to Oliveira (1994).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have a responsibility not only to provide quality education but also to contribute to the betterment of society through community extension and outreach program (CEOP). This is why CEOP should be integrated into the HEI's mission and vision, as it complements the institution's instructional and research programs. Community extension services play a vital role in the development of communities. It serves as a bridge between the institution and the community, facilitating the transfer of knowledge, skills, and technology from the academic sector to the community. The goal is to empower individuals and communities by providing them with the necessary tools and resources to become self-sufficient and sustainable.

HEIs can develop strategies and initiatives that are aligned with the needs of the community. These initiatives could focus on education, health, environment, or livelihood, among others. The programs should aim to have a comprehensive impact and promote sustainable development. It is also essential to establish a strong partnership with the

community and involve them in the planning and implementation of these initiatives. Through community extension services, HEIs can make a significant contribution to society. By reaching out and touching the lives of communities, the institution becomes a catalyst for positive change. This not only benefits the community but also the institution itself as it strengthens its reputation and relevance in society.

CES enables higher education institutions to extend their educational programs beyond the boundaries of the classroom and touch the lives of communities and the environment. These programs have the potential to create self-sufficient communities through sustainable initiatives by transferring knowledge and technology. By providing CES, institutions can engage in a transformative emancipatory teaching and learning process within the discipline of critical pedagogy. As a result, CES has become an efficient tool not only in the field of research but also in increasing ontological collective action amidst individualistically dominated societal constructs.

CES is a critical aspect of a higher education institution's mission. It complements the institution's instructional and research programs and serves to contribute to the betterment of society. By establishing strong partnerships with the community and implementing sustainable initiatives, HEIs can become agents of positive change in their communities. In the Philippines, Community Extension Service refers to the programs and activities initiated by universities, colleges, and other educational institutions to address the needs of the local communities they serve. These programs aim to improve the quality of life of the people in these communities, promote social responsibility, and provide opportunities for students to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world settings.

The community project that the CES values most and that responds to essential human and communal needs. These are physiological needs that can be met by strengthening the community's health sector's ability to address potential issues; Safety and security are another group of human needs that can be met by an environmental program that is well-assessed, planned, and implemented for at least three to five years. Literacy will increase one's self-confidence and self-esteem, enabling them to become a highly productive member of their community. If these all-encompassing facets of man and community are given effective short- and long-term programs and services, they will eventually help create a sustainable, forward-thinking family and a functional community. The goal of CES projects is to provide services and programs that are consistent with the organizational plans and activities developed by each institute and to the college level. These plans and activities are logically aligned with the institution's vision and mission. To accomplish the primary and shared purpose of addressing the needs of the adopted community, it also utilizes the skills and knowledge of faculty and students.

Within the scope of a five-year plan, MVGFCs CEOP objectives are being worked toward, and the following generic indicators are being used to assess, analyze, and measure intervention: accessible and affordable community activities, objectivity, and continuity of programs, which includes tracking and evaluating progress and even revising plans as

necessary, and fostering a culture of volunteerism, connections, and collaboration with all potential stakeholders.

The impact on people's lives and the community it serves is the surest indicator of CEOP's efficacy. The primary determinant of its success is whether those in charge are receptive to and supportive of the demands of the community during the anticipated period of implementation. On the case of MVGFC, its CEOPs are anchored to its Research, Development and Extension (RD/E) Agenda which is focused on poverty alleviation. MVGFC believe that the marginalized sector in our society needs support for them to "stand at their own" and given the time and opportunity, improved quality life could materialize if the proper programs for them are formulated and implemented (MVGFC Manual, 2016).

The main area of intervention is anchored on providing livelihood to the residents because with these: health and nutrition will be improved; peace and order could be attained and ultimately through education; and knowledge will be enhanced and ultimately the environment will be protected and managed. According to MVGFC Manual of 2016, "We are committed to build a community of people living in harmony, caring one another, and protecting the environment to ensure that the future generation will enjoy the same resources as they have now and at the end inclusive growth and development will be attained."

The Central Luzon School of Nursing (CLSN, currently known as the Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges, Inc. (MVGFCI), the first nursing school in Region 3, was established in 1960 by educator, lawmaker, and diplomat Dr. Manuel Viola Gallego. The institution's guiding principle was that those who were less fortunate in life should be given complete opportunities for overall development to lead better lives and contribute to a better society. This idea was rooted in the institution's founding fathers. In addition, it said that "We believe in voluntarily sharing our individual and collective expertise and resources with the community to improve the quality of life" about the reformed institutions' educational philosophy on extensions. strong, observable presence, and management through movement. We support a 'hands-on' management approach that entails being there where the action is taking place while monitoring, assessing, analyzing, interacting, inquiring, probing, learning, and comprehending the situation, problem, and needs" (MVGFCI, 1990).

MVGFCI adopted Barangay Talipapa for its Research and Extension Program on July 11, 2019, however because of the COVID 19 pandemic, not much was accomplished. A General Assembly of leaders took place on Saturday, August 6, 2022, at precisely 3:00 pm at the Barangay Chapel. Members of the Barangay Council, the SK Chairman, barangay workers like day care providers, BNS, BPO, and Purok Leaders, as well as representatives from PTA, Senior Citizens, Persons with Disabilities (PWDs), Parents Committee, and the Barangay Pastoral Council, attended the gathering. The major goals of the meeting were to identify requirements and challenges, recommend projects and potential solutions, and identify resources and competencies by industry. The MVGFC representatives grouped the participants into four groups based on common requirements

or industry sectors. The participant was able to identify three (3) prominent concerns that need to be addressed after an hour of the workshop: livelihood, waste management, and learning gaps (particularly in reading).

On June 20, 2022, the first meeting with the Talipapa Elementary School parents took place. A brief program was organized by the school staff and 13 parents attended. MVGFC received support and thanks from Barangay Captain Mirasol Dela Cruz and Mr. Henry Medrano, the school's principal, for their efforts to assist in the education of the parents. Mrs. Ma. Victoria R. Victa described the collaboration between the parents, Barangay Council, Talipapa Elementary School, and MVGFI to further the educational growth of their children through the Tulong Dunong Program.

A brief history of the learning areas that would be the focus was provided by Dr. Irene Apolinario of the Institute of Teacher Education (ITE) and Ms. Rochelle Sabado, an ITE graduate student. To further examine the areas of partnership for the Tulong Dunong Project, a consultation meeting was held on July 15, 2022, with the school head and teachers of Talipapa Elementary School.

During a courtesy call, Mrs. Ma. Victoria R. Victa, the Officer-in-Charge of Community Extension and Outreach at MVGFCI, discussed the "Tulong Dunong Project" (later renamed the 'Alalay sa Pagbasa Program') with the new principal of Talipapa Elementary School, Mr. Harron Dave S. Antonio. The Department of Education, responsible for the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in the region, was also present during the preliminary discussion.

Mr. Antonio welcomed the proposed intervention of teaching parents of struggling readers in Grades 5 & 6 but suggested that parents of non-readers in Grades 1 to 4 should be taught how to tutor their children at home, as challenges in reading should be addressed at the primary level. He also proposed that students of Teacher Education from MVGFC could tutor the struggling readers in Grades 5 & 6, given their practice teaching. They agreed to identify the parents and pupils involved to gather basic data for preparation, with further consultation to follow leading eventually to multi-disciplinary forms of MVGFCs CEOP.

As private and public sectors collaborate to tackle the gaps created by the COVID-19 pandemic, measures are being taken to address the scale of the problem. One innovative approach presented is the MVGFCs CEOP, which was inspired by the founders' worldview. The research model used in this approach is Community-Based Participatory Action Research (CBPAR), emphasizing the importance of community participation in the three stages of research work: pre, actual, and post epoch.

This study supports the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which was adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015 and to Ambisyon 2040 of the Republic of the Philippines which aims to promote peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and in the future, through a global partnership among all countries, developed and developing (SDG 2030). The study recognizes that eradicating poverty

and other forms of deprivation must be accompanied by strategies that enhance health and education, reduce inequality, promote economic growth, tackle climate change, and preserve our environment, families, societies, and future.

The outcomes of this research can contribute to addressing the local situation by introducing a new approach to understanding local intervention and pedagogy and formulating and implementing academic and non-academic socio-political policies in accordance with the vision, mission, and goals of MVGFC. These goals include individual and social transformation, which is cited as number 16 in its educational philosophies: "We believe in voluntarily sharing our individual and collective expertise and resources with the community for the purpose of improving the quality of life." Furthermore, the findings of this study can be beneficial to local policymakers in uplifting the lives of the people in Barangay Talipapa, while also aligning with the overall objectives of the national and international community.

The objective of this research is to help address the gaps that have emerged from the two-year lockdown resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. It aims to contribute to the ongoing efforts of MVGFC to improve the lives of its partner community in the face of the current complexity of the world and the Philippine society. The general objective of this paper is to document the MVGFCs CEOP made at Barangay Talipapa, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija from the period of March 2022 to August 2023. On the other hand, specific objectives are the following: to assess the needs, problems, and capabilities of the people of Barangay Talipapa; to assess the level of commitment of the people of Barangay Talipapa towards individual and social transformation; to evaluate the effectiveness of the MVGFCs CEOP from March 2022- August 2023; and to formulate effective and efficient academic and non-academic policies in terms of community extension.

In the case of Barangay Talipapa, we will be utilizing the Problem-Based Approach (PBL) because it focuses on the consolidation of raw feedback and reflection on the learning process. This approach is centered on group and collective dynamics, which are essential components in creating knowledge at both the individual and collective levels. According to Fostnot (1996), the process of learning is self-regulatory, and it involves reconciling personal models of the world with new insights encountered. This leads to the development of new representations of reality through cooperative social activity, discourse, and debate, resulting in meaning-making.

PBL places a greater emphasis on the learning process rather than solely acquiring knowledge, with an emphasis on interpersonal skills and communication. To achieve collective transformation, individuals must communicate and share information regularly. Social workers play a key role in facilitating an open dialogue, addressing communication barriers, and guiding the discussion. Critical dialogue is a primary means through which individuals can discover and redefine their world, which requires self-reflection and engaging in dialogue with clients. Important elements of critical dialogue include active listening, mutual trust, equality, patience, critical thinking, and a belief in the clients' ability to make positive changes (Christian & Jhala, 2015).

The core of Freire's theory is the concept of conscientization, which involves the power to transform reality through critical reflection on one's own world, perceptions, and reality, by perceiving the relationships among objects and their reasons for being. The dialectical approach, which involves cooperation between internal and external actors, can make the conscientization process feasible. According to Freire, consciousness is fragmented knowledge, while conscientization is a process of critical reflection that helps individuals become aware of their own worldview and reality. To sum up, the key concept of CEOP involves merging the influential impact of conscientization theory in education and social work. The implementation of this theory by universities and colleges in practice aims to achieve ontological liberation. CEOP aims to encourage critical pedagogy to foster a positive transformation in the lives of people and communities through cooperative intervention and education that promotes emancipation.

Research Questions

1. Was MVGFC-CEOPs extension of knowledge significant?
 2. Was there a manifestation of alignment and integration on instruction, research, and extension on MVGFCs CEOP?
 3. Is there any ground for MVGFC-CEOP to continue its extension program?
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METHODOLOGY

The exploratory nature of the research justifies the use of qualitative research methods. To ensure the quality of the study, MVGFCs CEOP and RDO approved tools such as profiling and skill assessment instruments, questionnaires for individual and group interviews, and other relevant methods were utilized.

The researcher has opted to utilize qualitative research methodology, which involves gathering and analyzing non-numerical data (such as text, video, or audio) to gain an understanding of concepts, opinions, or experiences. This approach is frequently employed in the humanities and social sciences, including fields such as anthropology, sociology, education, health sciences, and history. One reason for choosing this research design is its flexibility and ability to retain rich meaning when interpreting data. To evaluate parents' understanding of the multi-disciplinary CEOP approach, the researcher conducted Focus Group Interviews (FDIs), Individual Interviews (IIs), Reflective Approaches (RAs), and Empirical Observations (EOs).

It is important to note that although the research design chosen is Community-Based Participatory Action Research (CBPAR), it is still aligned with the eight (8) approaches of Conscientization Theory. These approaches, such as grounded theory, ethnography, action research, phenomenological research, and narrative research, share some similarities but have different aims and perspectives. Additionally, CBPARs approach, developed by DA-BAR, aims to transfer, and adopt technologies from research to farmers' utilization. This program enhances the role of research and development in technology transfer and production management, institutionalizes the active community participation

in the management of farm and coastal resources, and develops strategies for effective integration of support services for enterprise and agribusiness development.

To gather socio-demographic information, needs assessment and profiling was used. In April 2022, the Office of Cabanatuan City Planning and Development (OCCPD) conducted a contemporary data assessment to evaluate the initial status and level of social condition of the people of Barangay Talipapa. The data were provided by the local government unit of Nueva Ecija and were crucial in identifying the needs of the community. Using the data collected, the CEOP was able to identify the areas that require improvement in Barangay Talipapa. These areas may include infrastructure, healthcare, education, and social services. To address these issues, MVGFCs CEOP recommended updating the current Barangay Profile.

Updating the Barangay Profile will involve close coordination with the members of the Barangay Council and the partner community. It is important to have the participation of the community in updating the profile to ensure that their needs and concerns are properly reflected. The updated Barangay Profile can serve as a useful tool in the planning and implementation of development programs and projects in Barangay Talipapa. It can also serve as a reference for partner organizations and government agencies that may be interested in providing support and resources to the community. Moreover, the contemporary data assessment highlights the importance of data-driven decision-making in community development. By collecting and analyzing data, it is possible to identify the needs of the community and develop effective strategies to address them.

The next phase is the processing stage wherein after identifying the issues and concerns of the community through a General Assembly, MVGFCs CEOP began implementing several steps to develop effective strategies for community development. The first step in the processing stage was the re-validation of the current Barangay profile. This is an important step because it ensures that the information collected about the community is accurate and up to date. The re-validation process involves verifying the data collected in the previous profile and updating it with new information. The second step was the re-validation of the supplemental data through the CPDO form presented to the Barangay Council. This form collects data on the community's demographics, infrastructure, social services, and other important factors that affect the community's well-being. By collecting this data, MVGFCs CEOP can develop a more comprehensive understanding of the community's needs and priorities. The third step was the preparation for a sectoral General Assembly. This involves identifying the different sectors of the community and holding separate General Assembly (GA) for each sector. This approach ensures that the specific needs and concerns of each sector are addressed and included in the community development plan. The fourth step was the re-institutionalization of MVGFCs CEOP. This involves signing a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with partner organizations and government agencies to formalize their commitment to support the development of Barangay Talipapa. The MOA serves as a framework for collaboration and resource sharing.

Finally, MVGFCs CEOP tapped potential stakeholders to support the development of Barangay Talipapa. This involves identifying organizations and individuals who have the capacity and willingness to contribute to the community's development. These stakeholders may provide financial support, technical expertise, or other resources to help implement the community development plan.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alalay sa Pagbasa

Mrs. Ma. Victoria R. Victa, the esteemed Director of the Community Extension and Outreach Program at MVGFCI, recently engaged in a courtesy call with Mr. Harron Dave S. Antonio, the newly appointed principal of Talipapa Elementary School. Their discussion revolved around the transformative "Tulong Dunong Project," subsequently rebranded as the "Alalay sa Pagbasa Program." This program has a profound mission – to provide essential assistance to struggling readers within the community.

Mr. Antonio, the visionary principal, proposed a strategic shift in program focus, suggesting that it should target the parents of non-readers in Grades 1 to 4. He astutely recognized that the foundation for successful reading skills must be laid at the primary levels. In a brilliant twist, he advocated for equipping parents with the skills to guide their children's reading journeys at home, believing this approach would yield greater efficacy than direct intervention with struggling readers. Furthermore, he envisaged Teacher Education students from MVGFC contributing to the program by tutoring Grades 5 and 6 students as part of their practice teaching courses. They concurred on the need to identify beneficiaries, including both parents and pupils, to collect crucial baseline data for program preparation.

Consequently, the official beneficiaries of the Alalay sa Pagbasa Program expanded to encompass the parents of non-readers in Grades 1 to 4, along with the struggling readers in Grades 5 and 6. This marks a pivotal moment in addressing the reading challenges faced by the students of Barangay Talipapa. By targeting both parents and students, a collaborative effort is forged, dedicated to enhancing the children's reading skills, ultimately fostering improved academic performance. The involvement of MVGFC's Teacher Education students promises a dual benefit – aiding struggling readers and offering invaluable practical experience to future educators. The ultimate success of this program hinges on the active participation and cooperation of all beneficiaries and stakeholders.

Additionally, complementing the supplementary feeding packs, the City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO) launched a Food for Work project to address hunger among Talipapa Elementary School pupils. The project, bolstered by a generous contribution of P 13,000.00, also received support from the Banatu Elite Eagles Club with a contribution of P 4,500.00, and a donation of P 2,500.00 from Ms. Juliet Tabonan. These

donations are indispensable to the program's success, ensuring that the young residents of Cabanatuan City receive the nutrition necessary for their holistic development.

In an exceptional collaboration with the Cabanatuan City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO), led by the dedicated Mrs. Helen S. Bagasao, an additional ten parents joined the initial four in the inaugural community gardening endeavor. In recognition of their dedication, they qualified for the Food for Work program, entailing two family packages valued at P1,240.00 each. These packages would be distributed upon completion of their five-day engagement in community gardening at Talipapa Elementary School. The school's active participation in the Department of Education's school-based gardening initiative, facilitated by CSWDO's local link, Ms. Rhelaine Ocampo, signifies a commitment to holistic education and community development.

The Institute of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences, alongside its esteemed faculty and students, added a significant dimension to the program by conducting a meticulous weighing program for the participating pupils. The ITE's Alalay sa Pagbasa Project emerged as a cornerstone of the Community Extension and Outreach Program, intersecting with the objectives of various institutes. Initially led by Mr. Lou Santos from the ITE Faculty for Grades 1-4, this intervention spanned three months, commencing with 14 parents as active participants. While external factors such as scheduling conflicts, job commitments, and personal obligations led to a gradual decline in participation, initial significant impacts were observed among the parents of Grades 1-4 and the pupils of Grades 5-6 at Talipapa Elementary School.

The initial phase faced challenges, including schedule constraints and the absence of a comprehensive intervention plan and evaluation tool. Consequently, Mr. Santos had to withdraw from the project, leading to the introduction of the Phil IRI as a replacement, albeit introduced late in the year 2022.

In January 2023, following an in-depth assessment, the decision to entrust the pilot project's implementation to MVGFC High School was made. The MVGFC High School Department successfully maintained and managed the participation of the four parents involved throughout the year. To address the challenge of providing alternative work opportunities and equipping beneficiaries with new skills, livelihood training programs were introduced.

Meanwhile, Mr. Santos assumed responsibility for the reading tutorials for Grades 5-6, assisted by five dedicated ITE students. However, the absence of a structured outline for the reading tutorials posed a challenge, impacting the effectiveness of the intervention. Despite the shortcomings noted in the initial phase, parents of Grades 1-4 and pupils of Grades 5-6 at Talipapa Elementary School reported noteworthy positive impacts.

The Alalay sa Pagbasa Program at Talipapa Elementary School strives to augment the reading skills of both students and parents through two distinct components. Initially led by Mr. Louis Santos, the first part involved providing reading intervention to parents of

Grades 1-4 and engaging ITE student volunteers with Grades 5-6 students. However, due to scheduling conflicts for the A.Y. 2022-2023 Second Semester and the inadequacies of the evaluation tool, the intervention for parents of Grades 1-4 transitioned to the MVGFC High School Department after three months.

The MVGFC High School Department embraced a more systematic and scientific approach to the program, featuring a concrete lesson plan and utilizing the Phil IRI evaluation tool. This seamless transition underscored the significance of having a well-defined plan and evaluation system to ensure program efficacy.

The second part of the program involved reading tutorial sessions, where ITE students devoted at least an hour to Talipapa Elementary School. Regrettably, a structured outline and evaluation tool were absent, undermining the intervention's potential. To heighten the program's effectiveness for parents of Grade 1-4, it is advisable to develop a robust evaluation tool for both program segments. Such a systematic and scientific approach will undoubtedly lead to enhanced support for students and parents in their reading journey, ultimately improving academic performance. By addressing these weaknesses, the reading intervention program can expand its reach and make a more significant impact, truly meeting the needs of the Gallegan community residents.

Concurrently, Mr. Santos continued to oversee the reading tutorials for Grades 5-6, aided by ITE students. However, the absence of a structured outline for the reading tutorials remained a challenge, hindering the intervention's effectiveness. A structured outline would provide guidance, ensuring that reading tutorials are organized, engaging, and tailored to the specific needs of Grades 5-6 students.

Recognizing the imperative of sustainability and empowerment, MVGFC High School introduced livelihood training into the project. This additional facet seeks to equip participants with new skills and knowledge, thereby expanding their employment opportunities or enabling them to engage in income-generating activities.

The livelihood training programs offered by MVGFC High School serve as a practical solution to the limited work options faced by project-involved parents. These programs encompass entrepreneurship, vocational skills, and specific trades, equipping beneficiaries with the tools to pursue alternative livelihoods. This approach not only enhances economic prospects but also nurtures self-reliance and resilience within the community.

Moreover, by integrating livelihood training, MVGFC High School showcases a holistic approach to community development, recognizing that sustainable initiatives must encompass practical application of skills and knowledge. This comprehensive approach ensures that beneficiaries receive not only theoretical instruction but also the opportunity to apply their newfound skills.

Through collaborative efforts between MVGFC High School and committed parents, the project transcends immediate needs, emphasizing long-term sustainability. By

amalgamating education, community engagement, and livelihood training, the project aspires to generate a lasting impact that endures beyond the pilot phase.

Nevertheless, ITE Student Volunteers' reflections underscored the positive impacts witnessed despite the acknowledged shortcomings. Their individual evaluations highlighted the strengths and weaknesses observed during the program.

“On my first day of tutoring, I had the pleasure of working with three students: Jaycee, Angelo, and Arlene. Jaycee and Angelo are both in Grade 5, while Arlene is in Grade 6. To assess their reading abilities, I prepared some materials for them to read in both Filipino and English. During the session, I observed that Arlene had difficulty pronouncing English words, while Jaycee showed great knowledge and proficiency in reading. Angelo, on the other hand, struggled with reading even in his native language, but all three students were eager to learn and showed potential for improvement. Despite their differing abilities, I found that all three students were committed to their studies and were doing their best to learn. As a tutor, it is my job to provide them with the support they need to succeed, regardless of their starting point. With continued effort and guidance, I am confident that all three students will be able to make progress and reach their full potential” (Adam, 2023).

“It has been almost seven months since we started tutoring the students of Talipapa Elementary School, and I am pleased to see that my students have shown significant progress. Despite meeting them only once a week, I am proud to witness that a sizable portion of my students are learning new things and are able to read words that they previously found challenging. The transformation in their reading skills is remarkable, and it is heartening to see them read more quickly and proficiently than before. Throughout this tutoring program, I have observed distinct changes in each of my students. From the first day of our session, I have noticed the difference in their skills and abilities, and I am grateful to have been part of this journey. Jaycee has proven to be quite knowledgeable and proficient in reading, while Angelo initially struggled with reading even in Filipino but now reads more competently. Arlene, on the other hand, had difficulty pronouncing English words, but with patience and guidance, she has made notable progress” (Cruz, 2023).

“As a tutor, this program has provided me with the opportunity to gain teaching experience and enhance my skills as an educator. Witnessing my students' progress is immensely gratifying, and I am proud to have contributed to their development. Being part of this community service has enabled me to share my knowledge with students and make a positive impact on their lives. It has been an incredible experience to be part of their journey and see them grow, and I am grateful to have been a part of it” (Adam, 2023).

“I can say that the children have made great improvements because, from simple words to difficult words that they read, they are learning them. They became even more active and diligent when it came to school” (Tayao, 2023).

“During the initial meeting with my students, I observed that many of them struggled with various weaknesses. Specifically, I noticed that they were slow in reading English texts and had difficulties with letter sounds, understanding meanings of words, and spelling. However, over the past few months of teaching, I have seen remarkable progress in their reading skills. The children are eager to learn and have shown enthusiasm and enjoyment during our tutoring sessions. I believe their motivation and satisfaction have been boosted by the fun activities we do before the teaching starts and the rewards they receive afterward. Despite the positive developments, we have encountered some challenges along the way. Some children have not been able to attend school regularly, which affects their progress. We have also faced difficulties due to the lack of teaching materials and limited teaching time. Despite these obstacles, I remain committed to helping my students improve their reading skills and overcome these obstacles. Teaching these children has been a fulfilling experience for me as well. I have learned how to be patient, creative, and resourceful in my teaching methods. Seeing my students' progress and excitement in learning has been rewarding and has motivated me to continue doing community service” (Mercado, 2023.)

“When evaluating the students, I have noticed several strengths that they possess. Firstly, their willingness to learn how to read English effectively is evident. I have observed how the students participate actively in our tutorials, reading little by little and taking in the reading advice we give them. This eagerness to learn is a key strength that will serve them well in the future. Another strength that I have seen is the progress they have made in their reading mastery. Our guidance and tutorials as teachers have helped the students improve their reading skills significantly. In fact, my two students have shown marked progress in their reading, and my classmates have also shared stories of their students' reading mastery improvements. It's gratifying to know that our efforts are making a positive impact on these young learners. Lastly, I am impressed by the students' attentiveness during our tutorial sessions. They pay attention and actively participate, demonstrating their desire to learn more about reading. It's clear that they are taking their education seriously and are motivated to improve themselves. Overall, I am proud of the progress they have made and excited to see how much more they can achieve with our continued guidance” (Macasero, 2023).

“Throughout the entire journey of teaching the kids how to read, it was such a great experience for me who's aspiring to become a teacher. Our students became progressive in learning how to read although it might be too slow. A progress is still a progress no matter how slow or fast it is. I am glad that I was given a chance to be part in this kind of community service since it felt so good to share your knowledge with other people, especially to kids. Reading plays an important role in education because it is our weapon to be knowledgeable. This community service that MVGFC had perpetrated is helpful and hopefully, the Institute of Teacher Education would continue to do it so that no students would be left behind” (Macasero, 2023).

“Our observation in our first teaching to elementary school students in Talipapa was that most of their weaknesses were reading comprehension, spelling words, etc., and I am happy because they are gradually getting past these stages or trials of theirs as students.

And I was happy because I saw from the beginning to the end that they were willing to learn every day that we would teach them. And their strength that I saw is that they show loyalty, honesty, and are cooperative students with us as student teachers. They show respect to us. Now, even though I know I'm still a little far from my dream of becoming a teacher, they have been one of the things that inspired me to continue with my course” (Cruz, 2023).

These observations are consolidated below:

Strengths:

- The willingness of students to participate, activeness, and eagerness to learn.
- Progress in reading skills, even though some students started as slow readers.
- Students' attentiveness and commitment to learning.

Weaknesses:

- Students' slower reading pace, particularly in unfamiliar words.
- Lack of mastery in alphabet letters impacting reading proficiency.
- Limited teaching time due to one-hour sessions.

Recommendations:

- Continuation of the Alalay sa Pagbasa program.
- Increase in tutorial duration to two hours per session.

Despite the obstacles, the collaboration between the Cabanatuan City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO) and parents involved in the community gardening project stands as a testament to collective commitment. The Food for Work program, facilitated by CSWDO, rewards parents for their dedication to the community gardening initiative, showcasing a shared determination to uplift the local community. The school's active involvement in the Department of Education's gardening program further underscores its holistic approach to education and community development, with diligent monitoring by CSWDO's local link, Ms. Rhelaine Ocampo, ensuring progress and effectiveness.

Integration on the Non-Teaching Staff

The office of the Community, Extension, and Outreach Programs in collaboration with non-teaching units such as the Student Affairs Office (SAO) and the library, as well as various school organizations, organized a storytelling event using Big Books to celebrate Library Week on November 29, 2022. The event also included a feeding program for the pre-elementary beneficiaries of Talipapa Elementary School, which was well-received by both the children and their parents. This event was an excellent marketing tool as it was focused on the future of their children.

Around 50 pupils participated in the activity, and it proved to be an effective way of marketing through the lead character "Manuel" in the play. The storytelling event was well-planned and executed, with the collaboration of the different units and organizations involved. It aimed to promote reading and literacy among young children and to provide a fun and engaging way of learning.

The inclusion of a feeding program was a thoughtful gesture that highlighted the school's concern for the welfare of the community. This added element created a positive impact on the event's overall success, as it provided an opportunity for the school to engage with the community and show its support.

Basic Journalism Workshop

On November 22, 2022, the Office of the Institute of Teacher Education (ITE) responded to the request of Talipapa Elementary School (TES) to conduct a Basic Journalism Workshop for their pupils. The request was granted, and Mr. Rene Boy E. Abiva was assigned to facilitate the workshop for the pupils who will be joining the District School Press Conference on December 15, 2022.

The workshop aimed to equip the pupils with the basic knowledge and skills in journalism, such as news writing, feature writing, and editorial writing. This would help them prepare for the competition and enhance their abilities to communicate effectively in writing. It is also an opportunity for the pupils to explore their passion for writing and develop their potential in the field of journalism.

The workshop was conducted on December 2, 2022, at (TES). Mr. Abiva facilitated the workshop for English and Filipino writing with the help of the school's English teachers. The pupils actively participated in the workshop, and they were able to learn the fundamentals of journalism and apply them in their writing exercises.

The Basic Journalism Workshop is an excellent initiative that supports the development of the pupils' skills and talents. It is also a testament to the commitment of the Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges Inc. in providing quality education and contributing to the betterment of the community. The workshop was concluded effective because 15 pupils of (TES) were able to join and won the District Press Conference. The school's 2nd place out of 7 participating schools is a clear indication of the workshop's effectiveness and the students' dedication. This success has also allowed the school to participate in the Division School Press Conference.

On the other hand, these manifests the foundation's commitment to empowering and supporting its adopted community through various programs and interventions has positively impacted the students' academic growth and development. The success of the workshop and the competition also reflects the foundation's dedication to promoting quality education and academic excellence.

Training on Digital Learning Tools

The partnership between the Institute of Teacher Education (ITE) and the Institute of Information and Communications Technology (IICT) in Talipapa is an example of how a multi-stakeholder approach can address complex educational issues. The workshop facilitated by Mr. Nikol Bernardino and 20 ITE students equipped stakeholders with the latest knowledge and skills to use digital technology in teaching and learning. The multi-stakeholder approach ensures solutions are relevant, feasible, and sustainable, engaging different stakeholders such as educators, technology experts, and community members. The partnership between ITE and IICT highlights the role of technology in enabling communities to adapt to changing circumstances and promote inclusive and equitable education, bridging the digital divide. One tangible impact of the training on digital tools was the creation of Talimansi Dishwashing Liquid logo designed by one of the Alalay sa Pagbasa participants.

Digital literacy, or the ability to use technology effectively, is also important, especially for parents who play a critical role in supporting their children's learning. This underscores the need for comprehensive and sustained efforts in promoting digital literacy and inclusion, including the provision of training and capacity-building programs. The suggestion to coordinate and collaborate with Talipapa Elementary School and other government and non-government organizations to provide computers for parents is a practical and viable solution to address the digital divide. This initiative can also contribute to building partnerships and networks that can support future efforts in promoting equitable and inclusive education. The involvement of other stakeholders, such as NGOs and government agencies, can also bring in additional resources and expertise that can enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of the initiative.

Advance Journalism Workshop

The Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges Inc. responded positively to the request of Talipapa Elementary School's principal. On January 6, 2023, Mr. Rene Boy Abiva conducted a comprehensive training on campus journalism. The workshop aimed to enhance the knowledge and skills of the school paper advisers and student writers of TES in preparation for the Division School Press Conference.

The training session tackled different topics such as news writing, editorial writing, feature writing, and sports writing. Mr. Abiva also emphasized the importance of responsible journalism, ethical standards, and accuracy in reporting. The training was attended by 30 school paper advisers and student writers.

The success of the training session was evident in the results of the Division School Press Conference held on February 1-3, 2023, at Camp Tinio. Talipapa Elementary School won first place in the feature writing category, and three pupils qualified to join the preliminary screening for the Regional School Press Conference. The school and community members were grateful for the support and expertise provided by the MVGFC in their pursuit of academic excellence.

The Basic Journalism Workshop, with the help of the MVGFC, has effectively developed the pupils' skills and knowledge in journalism and reporting. The school paper adviser and principal's dedication and guidance are also crucial factors in the students' success. The foundation's continued support for the school reflects its commitment to promoting education and community development. Talipapa Elementary School's achievement can inspire other organizations and stakeholders to invest in promoting education and community development, particularly in journalism and communication skills among the youth. Overall, this success is a reminder of the importance of investing in education and community development and inspiring other organizations and stakeholders to collaborate towards this end. The success of one student from Talipapa Elementary School in passing the first screening for the Regional Press Conference is a significant milestone for the school and its journalism program. This achievement is a testament to the effectiveness of the Basic Journalism Workshop in developing the skills and knowledge of its students.

Seminar- Workshop for Creative Writers

The book project entitled "TALIPAPÂ: Antolohiya ng mga Tulâng Pambatà" is a collaborative effort that involved various literary contributors from different levels and institutions. The book aimed to increase the knowledge and creative skills of the pupils of Talipapa Elementary School, as well as to promote general literacy, which is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations.

The literary contributors from Talipapa Elementary School are Briana S. Tabora, Mary Luna T. De Guzman, Lance Andrei DC. Legado, Eurie Jhane D.S. Garcia, Samantha Faith V. Reyes, Princess Elize B. Sunio, Cyrex S. Dela Cruz, Clowie Dain B. Relucio, Ethan Dyezel C. Maple, Precious Love R. Salvador, Amethyst Amber B. Eslaya, Zia Khryzzamae DC Legaspi, and Ivy Clarise G. Tique. Meanwhile, the contributors from the MVGFC High School Department are Denella Denise C. Calderon, Allen S. Francisco, Danielle Angelo Sarte, Izziri Shantei Andres, and Jhaemine C. Domingo.

Faculty members from both the high school and tertiary levels of MVGFC also contributed to the book project. The faculty contributors are Dr. Ruth C. Alfonso, Nikol Reyes Bernardino, Jennelyn Dionisio, Johnwell Español, Ma. Victoria R. Victa, RSW, and Jhoar DC Gonzales. ITE students also participated in the project, namely Ronalyn M. Cruz, Donnalén V. Macasero, Shenalyn Pascual, and Rhea Mae Tayao.

The MVGFC Creatives Office, composed of talented and experienced graphic designers and artists, were tasked with the crucial responsibility of designing and laying out the book cover. With their expertise in creating visually stunning and impactful designs, they were able to craft a cover that perfectly captures the essence of the book and draws the reader's attention. The team worked closely with Mr. Abiva, the chief editor, and other stakeholders to ensure that the cover design reflects the book's themes and messages.

To ensure the quality of the book, author-writer and ITE faculty Mr. Abiva served as the chief-editor of the project while Professor Ronnel V. Talusan of Far Eastern University

(FEU) and Mrs. Marites Rogado of Linangan sa Imahen, Retorika, at Anyo (LIRA) served as external critics. He collaborated with Dr. Ruth C. Alfonso of the Institute of Teacher Education (ITE) and the publication section of Samahang Lazaro Francisco (SLF) for the copyediting and proofreading of the book manuscript.

100 copies were published, and the book project was made possible through the support of various institutions, including the Knights of Rizal (Naga and Cabanatuan City Chapter), Independent Order of Odd Fellows (Kafagway and Nueva Ecija Odd Fellows Lodge No. 38), Freemasons (Logia Soberanya Independiente Masonerya, Palayan Masonic Lodge No. 331, and Cabanatuan City Masonic Lodge No. 53), and Knights of Pythias. They donated money amounting to P15, 750.00. The book was published by 7 Eyes Production (OPC) with ISBN 978-621-8194-47-2 from the National Library of the Philippines (NLP), and it is now available to the public.

The book launching of "Talipapa: Antolohiya ng mga Tulang Pambata" was launched on May 30, 2023. The event was attended by contributor writers and illustrators from TES and MVGFC High School Department and ITE. Parents of the contributors from Talipapa Elementary School including MVGFC, DepED-SDO Cabanatuan City, and Barangay Talipapa officials joined the event.

Dr. Soledad M. Roguel, PhD, Director of the MVGFC Research Office commended the exceptional efforts of the school and its students in producing such a remarkable anthology. In addition, Brgy. Chairman Mirasol Dela Cruz and SGOD Chief Wilfredo R. Sison, EdD expressed their support and congratulations to the young poets, acknowledging the significance of the book as a source of inspiration for the creativity and imagination of elementary pupils. They pledged their commitment to support the book by means of re-printing and distributing it throughout the entire district of Cabanatuan City. Furthermore, the DepEd Officers of Cabanatuan recognized the book as a best practice within the district and explored the possibility of distributing it at the regional and national level, suggesting the need for a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA).

One of the highlights of the event was the book signing session, a special moment that allowed the young poets to autograph copies of the anthology for the attendees. This interactive session not only provided a personal touch but also allowed the students to experience a sense of accomplishment and pride as they shared their work with others. It was a heartwarming sight to witness the joy and enthusiasm on the faces of the young poets as they signed their names, embracing their roles as published authors.

The significance of the event extended beyond the school grounds, as it garnered substantial attention and recognition. The DepEd Region 3 News Network televised the event throughout Region 3, allowing a wider audience to appreciate the remarkable achievements of Talipapa Elementary School. Mae Belle Ebuena, the Media Chief of DepEd- SDO Cabanatuan City, played a crucial role in ensuring comprehensive coverage of the event. The televised coverage reached an estimated 41,300 viewers online, bringing the creative endeavors of the young poets to a larger audience. Furthermore, on June 5, contributors from Talipapa Elementary School and their adviser, Mrs. Revelyn

Chua, were invited for an interview on Dep-Ed Hour. This interview, which aired on June 7, attracted 9,789 viewers online, providing further exposure for the book and the talented young poets behind it.

During the Division Management Committee Meeting of SDO Cabanatuan City on June 26, 2023, the representatives of MVGFC were formally recognized for their program supporting Talipapa Elementary School. The division aims to extend similar assistance to more schools in Cabanatuan to benefit from such initiatives. They expressed their appreciation and acknowledgment to MVGFC for their valuable contributions to Talipapa Elementary School. On the other hand, they express their commitment in replicating and expanding the Antolohiya Project on all schools under their jurisdiction. MVGFC expressed their gratitude towards DepEd- SDO Cabanatuan City for acknowledging their efforts and for recognizing the positive outcomes of their program at Talipapa Elementary School. The recognition not only validates their hard work but also motivates them to continue their mission to assist more schools and students in the future. The presence of Schools Division Superintendent Dr. Catalina Paez and Division Chief Priscilla Sanchez further added to the significance of the project and event. The support and encouragement of her office inspire both educators and external partners to actively engage in educational initiatives for the betterment of the community.

A consultation and finalization of MOA between SDO-DepEd Cabanatuan City and MVGFC was held last August 1 at MVGFC Conference Room. The participants are Ms. Teny Peralta (Executive Officer), Dr. Federico O. Perez (Presidential Adviser and Oversight Committee), Dr. Ruth Alfonso (Dean, ITE), Dr. Ingrid Calanno (Faculty, ITE), Mrs. Victoria R. Victa, RSW (CEOP Officer), Mr. Rene Boy Abiva (Program Coordinator, ITE), Ms. Sheila Marie B. Prieto (Representative, SDO-DepEd Cabanatuan City), and Ms. Cyrille Therese B. Monta (Representative, SDO- DepEd Cabanatuan City).

On August 24, 2023, an impactful event unfolded at The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints on Del Pilar Street in Cabanatuan City - the 2023 Community Partnership and Ceremonial Signing of Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with Various Education Partners spearheaded by Department of Education, Cabanatuan City. Representing MVGFC were prominent figures such as Dr. Joseph L. Gallego, President of MVGFC; Ms. Estenily R. Peralta, Executive Officer of the President; Dr. Ruth R. Alfonso, Dean of the Institute of Teacher Education; Dr. Ingrid F. Calanno and Mr. Rene Boy Abiva, both esteemed ITE Faculty members; Mrs. Victoria R. Victa, Director of CEOP; and Ms. Erminda Esteban, an essential part of the Academic Staff. With an air of excitement and anticipation, the event commenced at 9:00 AM. Among the attendees were educators, representatives from various educational institutions, and local officials, all coming together for a common purpose.

Dr. Enrique E. Angeles Jr., a prominent academician with a PhD and CESO VI designation, took the stage to deliver an inspirational message. In his speech, Dr. Angeles emphasized the significance of partnerships in driving educational excellence and fostering holistic development among students. His words resonated with the audience, setting a positive tone for the rest of the event. The Schools Division Superintendent, Dr.

Catalina P. Paez, another accomplished educator holding a PhD and CESO V title, then addressed the gathering. Dr. Paez underscored the role of collaborative efforts between education institutions and the community in shaping the future of education. Her speech highlighted the importance of unity in achieving educational goals and enhancing the quality of learning experiences. Mr. Wilfredo R. Sison, PhD, the DepEd Chief of School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD), took the stage to introduce and present the various education partners participating in the event. With expertise in education administration, Dr. Sison provided insights into the collaborative endeavors these partners were set to undertake with the Department of Education (DepEd).

Leaders representing the Various Education Partners stepped forward to deliver their Statements of Confirmation, expressing their commitment to the shared goals outlined in the MOA. These leaders articulated their dedication to enhancing educational programs, improving access to resources, and supporting the holistic development of students in the community. The highlight of the event was the formal signing of the Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) between the DepEd and the Various Education Partners. This ceremonial act solidified the commitment of all parties involved to work together towards the betterment of education and the empowerment of students.

Following the MOA signing, a photo opportunity was provided, allowing attendees to capture the momentous occasion. Partners from both education and community sectors, as well as representatives from the DepEd, gathered for these memorable snapshots. The event concluded with closing remarks from the masters of ceremony from DepEd, Ms. Mae Belle Ebuena and Ms. Shiela Prieto. Their words expressed gratitude to all participants, highlighted the significance of the partnerships, and encapsulated the collaborative spirit that characterized the day.

The 2023 Community Partnership Cum Ceremonial Signing of MOA with Various Education Partners marked a remarkable step forward of MVGFC CEOP in the pursuit of educational excellence through collective efforts. It officially signaled a renewed sense of Gallegan purpose and dedication in shaping the future of education in Cabanatuan City. The signed MOA was officially turned over to MVGFCs CEOP by Dr. Cyrille B Domingo on September 15, 2023.

On a contrasting note, Mr. Rene Boy Abiva undertook a profound research endeavor titled "Conscientization, Pagpopook, at Pagpapakahulugan: Panimulang Kritisismong Post-Kolonyal sa Talipapâ: Antolohiya ng mga Tulâng Pambatâ." His research not only made a significant impact but also garnered recognition on multiple esteemed platforms. Firstly, this thought-provoking research secured its place at the 1st Research Forum held on August 9 and 10, where it clinched the prestigious title of "3rd Best Paper" in the Faculty Category. This accolade reflects Mr. Abiva's dedication and scholarly excellence.

Furthermore, the research paper transcended national borders, earning acceptance at the 1st International Multidisciplinary Conference on Research and Extension scheduled for September 19-22, 2023, at Batanes State College. This international recognition underscores the global relevance and intellectual significance of Mr. Abiva's work in the

realm of post-colonial criticism. Notably, the research continued to make waves as it found its place at the 3rd International Conference on Literature Education hosted by Palawan State University, taking place from October 26 to 28, 2023. This dual international exposure reaffirms the impact and relevance of Mr. Abiva's research, extending its reach to a diverse audience of scholars and educators.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

1. The success of the MVGFCs CEOP activities in improving reading skills in Barangay Talipapa exemplifies conscientization theory in action. By addressing the pupils' learning gap through targeted interventions, MVGFCs CEOP raised awareness and empowered the community to collectively tackle this issue. These efforts fostered critical thinking skills and sparked social change. Pupils gained improved reading abilities and self-awareness, while the community identified areas for further enhancement. This illustrates how education and collective action can drive positive change in a community.
2. MVGFCs CEOP success in Barangay Talipapa aligns with CBPAR. Through programs in livelihood and waste management, residents gained self-reliance, enhancing their economic and personal agency. Health initiatives improved physical well-being and community engagement. Encouraging responsible behavior increased youth and parental awareness, strengthening their sense of social responsibility. In essence, these efforts have empowered individuals to proactively shape their lives and community, showcasing the transformative power of collective action.
3. MVGFCs adoption of CBPAR highlights critical awareness and empowerment for personal and community betterment. In Barangay Talipapa, the community's eagerness to request seminars reflects their awareness of challenges and their proactive approach to addressing them. Collaboration with stakeholders provides resources and expertise, boosting their capacity and rapport. Empowerment fosters self-reliance, enabling better decision-making for community growth. This contributes to sustainable development and equity. With newfound knowledge and skills, the community becomes change agents, inspiring others. In essence, Barangay Talipapa's openness and collaboration align with conscientization theory, empowering individuals and communities for positive change and sustainable development.
4. MVGFC stresses the importance of community collaboration in development, exemplified by its CEOP work in Barangay Talipapa. Their joint efforts with the community and stakeholders have yielded positive results in livelihood, waste management, and education. Collaboration allows holistic, inclusive development, shared responsibility, and stakeholder involvement. It considers diverse ideas, leading to effective and lasting solutions. Collaboration empowers the community by involving them in planning and implementation, fostering pride, cooperation, and solidarity. It showcases MVGFCs CEOP commitment, building trust, and

ensuring sustainability. This collaborative approach reflects MVGFCs CEOP dedication to community development and its enduring partnership with the community.

5. MVGFCs CEOP one-year in Barangay Talipapa embodies their mission for sustainable development. Initiatives like promoting reading, digital learning, and staff integration align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This demonstrates MVGFCs CEOP commitment to quality instruction, research, and community extension. Collaborating with stakeholders ensures relevant, feasible, and sustainable programs. By engaging diverse stakeholders and promoting collective action, MVGFCs CEOP showcases how institutions can contribute to a better society and sustainable development.
6. Identified weaknesses in the MVGFCs CEOP highlight the need for enhancement. These limitations may have hindered program effectiveness and responsiveness to community needs. Addressing these weaknesses is vital for maximizing the programs' impact on individuals' lives. Refinement and improvement should involve revisiting program goals, strategies, and community feedback. This effort can lead to more extensive support, resources, and services, ultimately improving residents' quality of life. Continuous identification and correction of weaknesses are essential to better serve the community and create a significant positive impact on residents' lives.
7. MVGFCs CEOP emphasizes critical reflection and action for social change, relevant to community extension programs aiming to empower through education and action. Evaluating program effectiveness is crucial, especially for seminars and webinars whose impact may not be immediate. Long-term effects should be measured. In contrast, interventions like the Basic and Advance Journalism Workshop and Creative Writers Workshop have shown tangible transformation and impact by providing practical skills. These programs align with conscientization theory, offering tools for critical reflection and liberation. In summary, while seminars and webinars raise awareness, evaluating program effectiveness is vital. Programs providing practical skills have shown significant impact, aligning with MVGFCs goal of empowerment through education and action.
8. A well-designed lesson plan for Alalay sa Pagbasa and reading tutorials is crucial for effective interventions. While the ITE program had some impact, the MVGFC High School program's systematic approach was far more successful, retaining 4 out of 20 parents. Selecting the right faculty is vital for quality improvement and avoiding program weaknesses. Proper guidance during formative years is crucial for a child's academic success. Therefore, investing in well-designed and executed programs with the right resources and personnel is necessary to benefit students in need.
9. MVGFCs CEOP exemplifies the integration of academic programs for social relevance. The Alalay sa Pagbasa (ASP) initiative, conducted by MVGFC's Institute of Teacher Education (ITE) in Barangay Talipapa, aimed to address learning gaps caused by the pandemic. It involved parents of non-readers and a livelihood training program that led to the creation of Talimansi Dishwashing Liquid. Mr. Rene Boy Abiva and Mrs. Josefina O. Aranel conducted research on Project Talimansi's effects, earning recognition at MVGFC's Research Forum and at

international conferences. Furthermore, the Land Bank of the Philippines provided livelihood assistance to four active ASP and Project Talimansi participants, demonstrating the tangible benefits of academic-community-government partnerships in community development and assures the seal of good governance.

Recommendations

1. Proper documentation is crucial in the implementation of community service extension and policy making for several reasons. First, documentation serves as evidence of the activities, programs, and initiatives that have been implemented, which can be used to evaluate their effectiveness and make informed decisions about future actions. Accurate and detailed records of the implementation process can also help identify areas for improvement, identify best practices, and monitor progress towards goals. Second, documentation is necessary for accountability and transparency. It allows stakeholders, including community members, policymakers, and funders, to track the use of resources and ensure that the initiatives are aligned with the goals and objectives set. This transparency can help build trust and foster greater community involvement in the implementation process. Third, proper documentation can aid in continuity and sustainability. Documenting the implementation process and results can help ensure that the knowledge and experience gained can be passed on to future generations, and that programs and initiatives can be replicated or improved upon in the future.
2. To improve MVGFCs CEOP, it is necessary to conduct regular assessments and evaluations to identify areas for improvement. The programs should be designed to be more inclusive and accessible to a larger population in the community. Collaboration with other community organizations and stakeholders should also be strengthened to broaden the reach of the programs and achieve a greater impact. The programs should also be tailored to meet the specific needs of the community, and feedback from community members should be actively sought and incorporated into program development and implementation. Additionally, adequate resources should be allocated to ensure the sustainability of the programs and their long-term impact on the community.
3. To ensure the effectiveness of the reading intervention program at Talipapa Elementary School, it is recommended that a systematic and scientific approach be adopted. This includes the development of clear lesson plans and evaluation tools. Addressing the issue of the lack of lesson plans and evaluation tools will enable the facilitator to implement a more structured and goal-oriented intervention program that is better suited to the needs of the students and parents. By incorporating the Phil IRI evaluation tool and developing concrete lesson plans, the reading intervention program can be made more effective in addressing the students' reading needs. Additionally, providing training for the facilitator and ITE student volunteers on how to use the evaluation tool and implement the lesson plans will ensure that the intervention is delivered consistently and with quality. These recommendations, the reading intervention program at Talipapa Elementary School can become a more effective tool in promoting literacy and

empowering students and parents through education, ultimately leading to improved academic performance and long-term success.

4. Proper selection of an adopted barangay is essential in ensuring the success of community extension services without the interference of politics. The political status of the incumbent leaders in the barangay should be taken into consideration to avoid any compromising acts that may affect the delivery of community extension services. It is crucial to select a barangay where stakeholders, including government officials and community members, are committed to collaboration and are willing to work together towards the common goal of community development. The case of Barangay Talipapa serves as an example of how traditional politics can affect the long-term collaboration among stakeholders. The barangay had experienced conflicts and power struggles among its incumbent leaders, which had an impact on the delivery of community extension services. The involvement of politics in the barangay affected the cooperation and unity among stakeholders, hindering the development and progress of the community. By selecting a barangay with a stable political environment, community extension services can be delivered more effectively and efficiently. This can lead to better outcomes in terms of community development, as stakeholders are united towards a common goal without any political influence. The selection of an adopted barangay should be based on factors such as commitment to collaboration, willingness to work together, and a stable political environment to ensure the successful delivery of community extension services.
5. The inclusion of specific roles and responsibilities of the adopted Barangay in the Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) is crucial in ensuring the success of the partnership between the Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges and the Barangay. The commitment of the Barangay to send their constituents to enroll in the Foundation Colleges is a key factor in maximizing the full potential of the 5-year duration of the agreement. This will not only benefit the students by providing them with quality education, but also contribute to the development of the Barangay by producing competent and skilled individuals who can contribute to their community. Aside from the commitment to education, it is also highly recommended that the Barangay allocates a justifiable fund for community development, in addition to the collective efforts of all institutions outside its territory. This will ensure that the community receives necessary services and support for their growth and development. With proper allocation and utilization of funds, the Barangay can provide essential services such as healthcare, infrastructure, and livelihood programs to its constituents. Moreover, the collective efforts of institutions outside the Barangay can complement the Barangay's efforts, resulting in a more comprehensive and sustainable development of the community. By including these specific roles and responsibilities in the MOA, the partnership between the Foundation Colleges and the Barangay can establish a clear and mutually beneficial relationship. This will create a strong foundation for collaboration and ensure the effective implementation of community extension services.
6. The continuation of Alalay sa Pagbasa in Talipapa Elementary School is crucial in sustaining the progress and achievements made by MVGFCs CEOP. The CES

program is an essential component of the MVGFCs CEOP commitment to uplifting the community and aligning their extension program with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. MVGFCs CEOP program has already yielded tangible results, such as the successful journalism and creative writing workshops, which produced outstanding works that reached regional screening for journalism and resulted in the publication of a book with an ISBN by 7 Eyes Production (OPC). These accomplishments serve as a testament to the effectiveness of MVGFCs CEOP program in improving the skills, knowledge, rapport, and commitment of the community. Discontinuing the MVGFCs CEOP program in Talipapa Elementary School would be a significant setback for MVGFC, as it would mean losing the opportunity to further cultivate and enhance the skills, knowledge, rapport, and commitment established within the span of one year. The MVGFCs CEOP program's impact is not only felt within the community but also resonates throughout the institution, providing valuable learning experiences for both the students and the faculty. The continuation of Alalay sa Pagbasa in Talipapa Elementary School is essential to sustain and further the progress and achievements made by MVGFCs CEOP. It is a valuable investment in the community, the institution, and the SDGs, and should be prioritized and supported.

7. Selecting the right faculty to facilitate Alalay sa Pagbasa is crucial because they will be responsible for delivering the program and ensuring that students receive the guidance they need. It is important to choose faculty members who are knowledgeable in teaching reading and have experience working with young learners. A faculty member with a background in education or literacy instruction would be ideal, as they would have the necessary skills and expertise to design effective lesson plans and provide targeted support to struggling readers. Investing in the right faculty and resources for programs like Alalay sa Pagbasa is essential to maximize time and resources for quality improvement. Without proper guidance and instruction, the program may not be effective in helping students improve their reading skills. A well-trained and qualified faculty can ensure that students receive the necessary support and guidance, which can lead to more successful outcomes.
8. In addition, selecting the right faculty can help to avoid the weaknesses of the program. For example, if the faculty member is not skilled in designing effective lesson plans or does not have experience working with young learners, the program may be less successful in helping students improve their reading skills. By investing in the right personnel, the program can be tailored to meet the needs of the students, ultimately benefiting their academic success. This is a critical step in ensuring that the program is effective and achieves its goals. By investing in the necessary resources and personnel, the program can provide targeted support to struggling readers and help to improve their academic outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

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program of the Institute of Teacher Education of the Manuel V. Gallego Foundation Colleges. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest. The research does not contain any studies involving animals performed by any of the authors. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and that the results was used purely for research.

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Individual Informants/ Resource Persons

Dr. Harron Dave Antonio- *current principal of Talipapa Elementary School.*

Mrs. Racquel Samsom- *Grade 2 adviser in Talipapa Elementary School.*

Mrs. Rachel Chua- *Grade 4 adviser in Talipapa Elementary School.*

Mrs. Teresita Madjos- *MVGFC Assistant Librarian*

Ms. Jeah Basco- *faculty and CEOP coordinator for Institute of Business Management.*

Mr. Ralph Guevarra- *faculty and CEOP coordinator for Institute of Criminal Justice Education.*

Mr. Parco Culang- *faculty and CEOP coordinator for Institute of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences.*

Mr. Mark Roman- *MVGFC Creative's staff.*

Ms. Ivy Dela Cruz- *MVGFC student currently taking Bachelor of Science in Nursing.*

Ms. Donnaleen Macasero - *3rd year BSED-Filipino of the Institute of Teacher Education.*

Ms. Joanna Adam- *3rd year BSED -Filipino of the Institute of Teacher Education.*

Ms. Jasmine Mercado- *3rd year BSED -English of the Institute of Teacher Education.*

Ms. Ronalyn Cruz- *3rd year BSED -Filipino of the Institute of Teacher Education.*

Ms. Rhea Mae Tayao- *3rd year BSED -English of the Institute of Teacher Education.*
